

Nation Protecting Shrines

also known as “Gokoku Jinja”, “Gokoku Shrines”

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Entry tags: Mortuary shrine, Japonic, Shrines, Taiwan, Religious Group, Shintō, China, Japanese, Japan, Korea, Sakhalin, Ritual centre, Language, Secularism, Mausoleum, Religious Place, Japanese Religions, Shrine

Nation-protecting shrines, or gokoku jinja, were established in 1939 as regional branches of Yasukuni Jinja. After the Boshin War (1868-9), a new form of national veneration of the war dead began, drawing especially upon Shinto and Confucian traditions. These temporary spirit-summoning (shokon) sites spread and were eventually transformed into permanent shrines for venerating the collective eirei, or "glorious dead", of those who had given their life for the emperor and nation. Although nation-protecting shrines were legally Shinto shrines (jinja), they were distinguished from regular Shinto shrines by their veneration of the collective recent dead, their parallel but separate ranking system, and their joint management by the military and home office. The veneration of the war dead at Yasukuni Jinja and the gokoku shrines was one of the most visible manners in which the imperial state mobilized its subjects to war. During the American occupation of Japan, gokoku shrines were allowed to exist as private religious organizations but were required to strip the term "nation-protecting" from their titles. After the occupation, shrines could restore the term to their title, but the new religious framework for governing Shinto shrines largely erased the distinctions between gokoku shrines and regular Shinto shrines. For several years postwar, the war dead continued to be enshrined and in some cases new gokoku shrines were built as local war memorials (ex: Munakata Gokoku Jinja). Today, gokoku shrines have taken various approaches towards their role in contemporary society. Some shrines started enshrining those who died in the line of duty postwar, such as police officers and self-defense force members, while others have remained dedicated only to prewar eirei.

Date Range: 1939 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Japanese Empire and Occupied Areas

Region tags: Asia, North Asia, Southeast Asia, East Asia, Southeast Asia, Japan, China, East Asia, South Korea, Taiwan

Japanese colonies and occupied areas, focusing on places where gokoku shrines were founded in the 1940s.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Yasukuni Shrine: History, Memory, and Japan's Unending Postwar, by Akiko Takenaka (2015)
- Source 2: Local History and War Memories in Hokkaido, edited by Philip A. Seaton (2016)
- Source 3: Overseas Shinto Shrines: Religion, Secularity and the Japanese Empire, by Karli Shimizu (2023)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.yasukuni.or.jp/gokoku.html>
- Source 1 Description: Yasukuni Shrine Website List of Shrines
- Source 2 URL: <http://himoji.jp/database/db04/index.html>
- Source 2 Description: Research Center for Nonwritten Cultural Materials Database of Overseas Shrines

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Tree, grove, or forest

Notes: Gokoku shrines were often located near or on major Japanese imperial military bases, or next to the main shrine of the area. Shrine grounds were usually landscaped to provide an appropriately dignified forest to surround it.

Type of elevation

- Mountain

Notes: Gokoku shrines, especially overseas, were often located next to the general protector (sochinju) shrine of the area, which "watched over" the capital city it protected from a nearby mountain.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: During WWII, the construction of a gokoku shrine in the regional/colonial capital was a significant symbol of being an important regional center within the Japanese empire, along with the city hall, train station, public park, etc.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: No.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: The original plans usually included a group of structures, but later expansion plans for the site might be conducted in one or more stages.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: A surrounding garden was planned during the construction of gokoku shrines, like at other shrines during the mid-20th century. However, this garden may have been expanded in multiple stages in some cases.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: The main function was to commemorate the war dead, which took the form of veneration, in order to mobilize the populace for war. Postwar, gokoku shrines continue to serve multiple functions, including religious, memorial, social, and political aims.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: Unlike some Shinto shrines, gokoku shrines do not typically undergo a regular cycle of being torn down and then reconstructed.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: Most gokoku shrines still exist today, but those overseas such as in Korea and Taiwan have been torn down or repurposed.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: The war dead are collectively commemorated. It could be argued that their patriotic death for the nation has divinized them, but that sort of theology is not important to the site.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Notes: But as they were constructed under the modern ideal of the family-state, to a certain extent it can be said that all the glorious dead are "family" of the Japanese nation.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: The war dead are collectively commemorated.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Body present:

– No

Notes: There are rare exceptions, such as the cemetery at Hakodate Gokoku Jinja.

↳ Part of body present:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Notes: But as they were constructed under the modern ideal of the family-state, to a certain extent it can be said that all the glorious dead are "family" of the Japanese nation.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

–Other [specify]: Military

Notes: Many times, the sites began as a military commemoration (shokon) site, but they received permission and veneration from the emperor. Postwar, there are instances of community groups building gokoku shrines (e.g. Munakata Gokoku Jinja).

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Notes: During WWII, POW labor was used to help with shrine construction in some cases.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Notes: Most gokoku shrines originated as shokon sites. Many shokon sites were originally established to commemorate the war dead of a specific incident, but were expanded to include all war dead from that regional area. For example, Sapporo Gokoku Jinja originally commemorated the Hokkaido war dead who helped put down the Satsuma Rebellion of 1877.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: Gokoku shrines were usually funded through a combination of public money and donations from the populace. This included donations collected by Buddhist and Sect Shinto groups.

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: It aimed to pacify the spirits of the war dead (who had died an unnatural death), but also to ask for them for their support in the protection of Japan.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The honden, or sanctuary, is the most important structure at gokoku shrines.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Notes: But there are cases where shrines might boast of an especially large torii gate, such as Fukuoka-ken Gokoku Jinja's Ootorii.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes it is locally sourced, and sometimes superior material is brought from other places, such as Taiwan cypress.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Usually it is locally sourced, and sometimes material such as granite is donated from more distant places.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Ferroconcrete

Notes: Ferroconcrete was a popular material for shrines during the early twentieth century because it was a new "modern" material that could mimic the look of stone. It could also withstand earthquakes and termite damage better than materials like wood.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: For example, gold embossed caps on the end of wood beams to protect them (kazari).

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Gokoku shrines remain largely without permanent decoration inside, but might have small embellishments (kazari).

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Shrines might display votive paintings or other donations on the wall.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: But there may be statues of the "glorious dead", which have become kami.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: There may be statues related to the glorious dead, such as at Fukuoka-ken Gokoku Jinja. Or peace monuments on shrine grounds might feature humans.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Animals, especially bronze horses.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Votive paintings (ema) are on movable panels.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– No

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Specific historical narratives (ex: a certain battle) that have a deep connection to many of the war dead enshrined there might be made into a painting as a votive offering.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: They are done in calligraphy, often by a well known military commander.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: For example, there will be a pillar inscribed with the name of the shrine, or the names of those who donated to the shrine.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: The landscaping of the shrine garden, the choice of architecture, and so on can also be considered a part of the decoration.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: But there are exceptions such as Hakodate Gokoku Jinja, which includes a graveyard.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: It is for the veneration of the glorious dead (eirei), who died in the name of the Emperor. They are real people who died tragically.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

Notes: It is for the veneration of the glorious dead (eirei), who died in the name of the Emperor. As they are now collectively considered kami, you could argue that they have been deified, but the shrines themselves do to see eirei as "gods" in a western sense.

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Notes: It is for the veneration of the glorious dead (eirei), who died in the name of the Emperor. As they died for the Emperor and nation, they are considered heroes by the shrine.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: But gokoku shrines often hold relics (such as letters, pair of glasses, weapon, clothes) of their war dead in a museum or exhibit on shrine grounds.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: A gokoku shrine is a permanent home for the "glorious dead" which evolved from "shokon" rites, which previously had only temporarily invited the spirits of the glorious dead down.

Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Some people might claim to feel them, but that is not a formal part of gokoku shrines'

function.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: If we considered the "glorious dead" as "gods or supernatural beings", then visitors might silently communicate by expressing gratitude to them ("gods") through veneration. But I think many people would argue that the glorious dead are not exactly gods nor supernatural beings.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Variable

Notes: For example, at Hokkaido Gokoku Jinja's major festival on June 5, 1945, there were 156 ritualists and assistants, 1300 bereaved relatives, in addition to the uncounted members of the marching bands and regular attendees. (Shimemura 1981, 637-8) In 1954, around 8000 bereaved relatives attended the shrine's festival (Ibid. 762), while in 1979, around 300 local elites were recorded as attending the formal festival. (Ibid. 768)

Reference: Shimemura, Sadao. Hokkaidō Gokoku Jinja Shi. Asahikawa: Hokkaidō Gokoku Jinja, 1981.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Daily and with larger festivals taking place on a yearly cycle

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Notes: Shinto rituals include a small sip of "omiki" (sacred sake) at the end of formal veneration ritual. But this is not enough to intoxicate a person. Often a small bottle of omiki is sent home with the visitor, rather than being served directly to the visitor at the shrine.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: For example, both modern and antique swords were a common gift given to gokoku shrines.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: For example, regular offerings include food stuff such a rice, while everyday objects belonging to the enshrined war dead were donated to the shrine as relics.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: Currently, attendance is not mandatory. But during the prewar and wartime period, Japanese subjects--especially students and public officials--were expected to venerate at gokoku shrines in order to demonstrate their patriotism.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– No

Notes: While some famous shrines such as Ise Jingu have a tradition of undergoing a regular rebuilding (shikinen sengu), gokoku shrines do not have that tradition. This is probably due to their short history extending back only to 1939.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: During the wartime period, soldiers, students, and civil groups donated their labor as a patriotic act to help build and maintain the shrine.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

– obligatory for all

Notes: During the war time period, Japanese subjects were expected to venerate regularly at the shrine to demonstrate their patriotism. Now it is common for especially right-leaning citizens and politicians to visit Yasukuni jinja or more locally gokoku shrines, but it is not obligatory by any means.

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: In addition to monthly or daily lesser festivals, gokoku shrines generally celebrate their regular festival in Spring and/or Autumn as well as a major festival during obon season. During the war, a yearly "irregular festival" was conducted to enshrine new war dead.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Elites

– Only locals

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Elites and the war-bereaved usually participated in the major festivals, but during the wartime period all local members of society might take part in festival-related events.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Dependable

Notes: It depends upon the size of the local community and the number of new war-dead.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the size and economic condition of the shrine, it may have a fulltime or only part-time ritualist.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: Like at other Shinto shrines, ritualists at larger gokoku shrine are divided into head priest, assistant head priest, assistant priest, and trainees. Miko (shrine maidens) are not priests, but may assist with rituals and perform kagura dance. Smaller gokoku shrines may have only one priest (guji), or possibly no dedicated priest of its own.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: If the shrine is large enough, it will include a residence for the ritualist(s).

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: During the war, soldiers, school students, and civilian groups were organized through the military, school, or supporter organizations (respectively) to "donate" their labor to the shrine as way to contribute to the war effort. Today, priests and other staff take part in the regular maintenance of the shrine.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: During WWII, gokoku shrines were government institutions governed jointly by the military and the Home Ministry. As government funding of shrines was insufficient, shrines also depended upon supporter organizations and veteran groups to actively fundraised for the shrine, often in co-operation with the regional government. After WWII, gokoku shrines became private religious organizations and were prohibited from receiving government funding. Thus shrines rely upon their supporting organizations as well as income from private ceremonies such as weddings.

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Notes: Gokoku shrines were sometimes located directly next to general protector shrines, which often served as a location for community services overseas.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Especially, letters and memoirs of the "glorious dead".

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: specify: Variable, Shimemura, Sadao. Hokkaidō Gokoku Jinja Shi. Asahikawa: Hokkaidō Gokoku Jinja, 1981.